

Supporting information

Activity-Stability Relationship in Compositionally Tuned Magnetron Co-sputtered Bimetallic Catalysts for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells

Martin Orság¹, Athira Lekshmi Mohandas Sandhya¹, Xianxian Xie¹, Jan Kučera¹, Miquel Gamon Rodriguez¹, Yurii Yakovlev¹, Milan Dopita², Iva Matolínová¹, Ivan Khalakhan^{1,*}

¹ Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, V Holešovičkách 2, 180 00 Prague 8, Czech Republic

² Department of Condensed Matter Physics, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, 12116 Prague 2, Czech Republic

*Corresponding Author E-mail: ivan.khalakhan@mff.cuni.cz, khalakhan@gmail.com

Deposition parameters

Table S1: Deposition parameters for Pt_xM_{100-x} ($M = Co, Cu$ and Y) alloy catalysts.

	P_{Pt}/W	P_M/W	t/s
Pt ₁₀₀	60	0	450
Pt ₇₅ Co ₂₅	24	36	960
Pt ₅₀ Co ₅₀	17	45	1020
Pt ₂₅ Co ₇₅	11	52	900
Pt ₇₅ Cu ₂₅	20	15	1500
Pt ₅₀ Cu ₅₀	18	23	900
Pt ₂₅ Cu ₇₅	11	30	600
Pt ₇₅ Y ₂₅	30	32	1020
Pt ₅₀ Y ₅₀	20	62	840
Pt ₂₅ Y ₇₅	10	80	780

Calculation of platinum loading and specific power

The platinum loading for each sample was calculated as follows:

Denoting the atomic concentration of metal X as c_{atX} , its relative atomic mass as A_{rX} , its mass as m_X and the number of atoms of metal X in the alloy as N_X , then for Pt–M alloy we have

$$c_{atPt} = \frac{N_{Pt}}{N_{Pt}+N_M} = \frac{\frac{m_{Pt}}{A_{rPt}}}{\frac{m_{Pt}}{A_{rPt}} + \frac{m_M}{A_{rM}}} \quad (1) \quad \rightarrow \quad c_{atPt} \frac{m_{Pt}}{A_{rPt}} + c_{atPt} \frac{m_M}{A_{rM}} = \frac{m_{Pt}}{A_{rPt}} \quad (2)$$

$$m_M = \frac{m_{Pt}A_{rM}}{c_{atPt}A_{rPt}} - \frac{m_{Pt}A_{rM}}{A_{rPt}} = \frac{m_{Pt}A_{rM}}{A_{rPt}} \left(\frac{1}{c_{atPt}} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

Denoting the total mass of the catalyst as m , we can calculate the mass of platinum.

$$m_{Pt} = m - m_M = m - m_{Pt} \frac{A_{rM}}{c_{atPt}A_{rPt}} (1 - c_{atPt}), \quad (4)$$

$$m_{Pt} \left(\frac{c_{atPt}A_{rPt} + A_{rM}(1 - c_{atPt})}{c_{atPt}A_{rPt}} \right) = m \quad (5) \quad \rightarrow \quad m_{Pt} = \frac{m c_{atPt} A_{rPt}}{c_{atPt} A_{rPt} + (1 - c_{atPt}) A_{rM}} \quad (6)$$

Note that, as we consider bimetallic alloys: $(1 - c_{atPt}) = c_{atM}$ (7)

Although we observed deviations from Vegard's law for Pt–Y alloys, for simplicity in Pt loading calculations, we assumed that all alloys followed Vegard's law. Thus, the alloy density, ρ , is calculated as:

$$\rho = c_{atPt} \rho_{Pt} + c_{atM} \rho_M, \quad (8)$$

where ρ_X is the density of metal X.

We can derive the formula for the mass of platinum in the bimetallic alloy.

$$m_{Pt} = \frac{Sh(c_{atPt} \rho_{Pt} + (1 - c_{atPt}) \rho_M) c_{atPt} A_{rPt}}{c_{atPt} A_{rPt} + (1 - c_{atPt}) A_{rM}} \quad (9)$$

where S and h denote the active area of the fuel cell and the height of the catalyst layer, respectively. Platinum loading is

$$m_{SPt} = \frac{h(c_{atPt} \rho_{Pt} + (1 - c_{atPt}) \rho_M) c_{atPt} A_{rPt}}{c_{atPt} A_{rPt} + (1 - c_{atPt}) A_{rM}} \quad (10)$$